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“SDG GOALS: THE PRINCIPLES OF INTERGENERATIONAL EQUITY AND HOLISM”

The fundamental ethical principle behind sustainable development is equity, particularly intergenerational equity. Equity is all about fairness. Obtained from a concept of social justice. It represents a belief that there are some things which people should have, that there are basic needs that should be fulfilled, that burdens and rewards should not be spread too divergently across the community, and that policy should be directed with impartiality, fairness and justice towards these end (Falk, Jim, Hampton, Greg, Hodgkinson, Ann, Parker, Kevin and Rorris, Arthur. 1993, *Social Equity and the Urban Environment*, Report to the Commonwealth Environment Protection Agency, AGPS, Canberra, p.2). According to Weiss, 1990, p. 8, intergenerational equity is a concept that says that humans 'hold the natural and cultural environment of the Earth in common both with other members of the present generation and with other generations, past and future. That, we the present generation have the obligation to pass all that we have inherited from the previous generation, the resources and its natural attributes that we are enjoying to the future generation with utmost reasonable care.

Moreover, those who are poor and hungry will often destroy their immediate environment in order to survive: They will cut down forests; their livestock will overgraze grasslands; they will overuse marginal land; and in growing numbers they will crowd into congested cities. The cumulative effect of these changes is so far-reaching as to make poverty itself a major global scourge (World Commission on Environment and Development, op.cit., p.72). In such a manner that intergenerational equity is enforced across the world within one generation. And that the reason of intergenerational equity being the key principle for sustainable development is the inequities as a cause of environmental degradation in which poverty deprives the people of the choice on whether or not to be environmentally sound in their actions and inequality will remain as a major global challenge for all.

Thus, this is expressed in the two goals of sustainable development; such goals were attaining a just and lasting peace and in ensuring security, public order and safety (Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022). Wherein in attaining at least these two our country should promulgate and enact laws that are made to determine where one person's rights end and the next person's rights begin, that the government should continue its quest in its pursuit of lasting peace as well as to establish social and economic rights in which it includes people's rights relating to health and its socio-economic factors. As well as, for the attainment of this goals towards sustainable development in a holistic and fair approach for inclusive growth, globally competitive economy and resilient society along with peace, security and public safety. For ensuring all of this is a basal support in attaining the government's plan in enhancing the social fabric, reducing inequality and in greater potential for growth.

To this point, if equity is to be taken seriously then new ways of decision-making must be found that enable the multifaceted values associated with the environment to be fully considered and heeded. That every person of present and future generation will be living in an environment acceptable to his well-being and unsafe areas and communities will be protected and developed in any possible form for a better future.

